

(untitled)

Dear participant,

Thank you for taking this survey.

This questionnaire is a part of my master thesis project where I am analyzing why and how JavaScript developers use linters. By collecting enough answers, the published results will include advice for developers on how it is best to use these tools, and advice for tool makers on how to improve them. In the end of the survey you can register your email if you wish to receive the results of this study.

This survey takes 10-15 minutes to complete and the answers will solely be used in aggregated and anonymised form. When you have completed the survey you have a chance of winning an Amazon gift voucher worth 50 dollars.

Thank you,
Kristín Fjóra Tómasdóttir,
Delft University of Technology

About You

1. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Transgender Male
- Transgender Female
- Gender Variant / Non-conforming
- Other - Write In
- Prefer not to answer

2. What is your country of residence?

Afghanistan
Albania
Algeria
Andorra

Andorra
Angola
Antigua and Barbuda
Argentina
Armenia
Australia
Austria
Azerbaijan
Bahamas, The
Bahrain
Bangladesh
Barbados
Belarus
Belgium
Belize
Benin
Bermuda,
Bhutan
Bolivia
Bosnia and Herzegovina
Botswana
Brazil
Brunei
Bulgaria
Burkina Faso
Burundi
Cambodia
Cameroon
Canada
Cape Verde
Central African Republic
Chad
Chile
China
Colombia
Comoros
Congo, Democratic Republic of the
Congo, Republic of the
Costa Rica
Cote d'Ivoire
Croatia
Cuba
Curacao
Cyprus
Czech Republic
Denmark
Djibouti
Dominica

Dominica
Dominican Republic
East Timor (see Timor-Leste)
Ecuador
Egypt
El Salvador
Equatorial Guinea
Eritrea
Estonia
Ethiopia
Fiji
Finland
France
Gabon
Gambia, The
Georgia
Germany
Ghana
Greece
Grenada
Guatemala
Guinea
Guinea-Bissau
Guyana
Haiti
Holy See
Honduras
Hong Kong
Hungary
Iceland
India
Indonesia
Iran
Iraq
Ireland
Israel
Italy
Jamaica
Japan
Jordan
Kazakhstan
Kenya
Kiribati
Kosovo
Kuwait
Kyrgyzstan
Laos

Latvia
Lebanon
Lesotho
Liberia
Libya
Liechtenstein
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Macau
Macedonia
Madagascar
Malawi
Malaysia
Maldives
Mali
Malta
Marshall Islands
Mauritania
Mauritius
Mexico
Micronesia
Moldova
Monaco
Mongolia
Montenegro
Morocco
Mozambique
Myanmar
Namibia
Nauru
Nepal
Netherlands
Netherlands Antilles
New Zealand
Nicaragua
Niger
Nigeria
North Korea
Norway
Oman
Pakistan
Palau
Palestinian Territories
Panama
Papua New Guinea
Paraguay
Peru

Philippines
Poland
Portugal
Qatar
Romania
Russia
Rwanda
Saint Kitts and Nevis
Saint Lucia
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
Samoa
San Marino
Sao Tome and Principe
Saudi Arabia
Senegal
Serbia
Seychelles
Sierra Leone
Singapore
Slovakia
Slovenia
Solomon Islands
Somalia
South Africa
South Korea
South Sudan
Spain
Sri Lanka
Sudan
Suriname
Swaziland
Sweden
Switzerland
Syria
Taiwan
Tajikistan
Tanzania
Thailand
Timor-Leste
Togo
Tonga
Trinidad and Tobago
Tunisia
Turkey
Turkmenistan
Tuvalu
Uganda

Ukraine
United Arab Emirates
United Kingdom
United States
Uruguay
Uzbekistan
Vanuatu
Venezuela
Vietnam
Yemen
Zambia
Zimbabwe

3. What is your primary role in software development?

- Developer
- Tester
- Designer
- Project manager
- Team leader
- Manager
- Researcher
- Student
- Other - Write In

4. How many years of experience do you have in software development?

Type a number.

5. How many years of experience do you have with using JavaScript?

Type a number.

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists.

6. Is JavaScript one of your main programming languages?

- Yes
 - No
 - I don't use JavaScript
-

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Is JavaScript one of your main programming languages?" #6 is one of the following answers ("Yes","No")

7. Have you used JavaScript in the last 12 months?

- Yes
 - No
-

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Is JavaScript one of your main programming languages?" #6 is one of the following answers ("Yes","No")

8. Which field do you regularly work in, when working with JavaScript?

Check all that apply.

- Open source software
- Commercial software
- Other - Write In

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists.

9. Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?

- Yes
 - No
-

Linter Usage

10. How important do you think it is to use a linter in a JavaScript project?

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|------------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| Unimportant | Slightly important | Neutral/Not applicable | Important | Very important |
| <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |
-

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists. Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

11. Which linter(s) have you used?

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it.

- JSHint
 - JSLint
 - ESLint
 - JSCS
 - Standard JS
 - TSLint
 - Other - Write In
 - Other - Write In
 - Other - Write In
-

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("No")

12. Why have you not used a linter?

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

13. If you prefer to use one linter over another, please state which and explain why.

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

14. In your previous experience with using a linter, why did you use it? Rate your level of agreement with the following reasons.

If other reasons than those that are listed apply, please add them.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral/Not applicable	Agree	Strongly agree
To avoid giving negative comments while doing code reviews and thus sparing the developers' feelings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To maintain code consistency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To avoid ambiguous or complex code	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To catch bugs and/or typing mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To automate parts of a code review	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To learn about JavaScript features and/or syntax	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To save time on discussing code style	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Configuring a Linter

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

15. In your previous experience with using a linter, which method(s) did you use to select the rules that are included in the configuration file?

Check all that apply. If other methods than those that are listed apply, please add them.

- Use default configurations from the linter
- Use a preset (a set of configurations made publicly available by someone)
- Use a plugin (a set of custom rules made publicly available by someone)
- Choose rules that fit the current style of a project
- Have the linter automatically generate configurations that fit the project
- Enable rules that come up in discussions on a project (e.g. on a pull request or in an issue tracker)
- Choose the most commonly used style within team
- Try to have the configuration as minimalistic as possible
- Choose rules that involve the least effort to follow (e.g. by not having to bypass the rules too often)
- I don't care which rules are enabled, as long as there is a set of rules present in the project
- I have never configured a linter
- Other - Write In
- Other - Write In
- Other - Write In

LOGIC Show/hide trigger exists. Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

16. Do you generally prefer to use a preset (or default configurations) or to manually choose the rules in your projects?

A **preset** is a set of configurations made publicly available by someone.

Note that we only ask for **presets** and **default configurations**, and **not plugins**.

- Only a preset
- A preset with some rules added or removed
- Only manually chosen rules
- Not applicable
- Other - Write In

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Do you generally prefer to use a preset (or default configurations) or to manually choose the rules in your projects?"

A **preset** is a set of configurations made publicly available by someone.

Note that we only ask for **presets** and **default configurations**, and **not plugins**." #16 is one of the following answers ("Only a preset", "A preset with some rules added or removed", "Other - Write In")

17. Which preset(s) do you like to use?

A **preset** is a set of configurations made publicly available by someone.

Check all that apply. Note that we only ask for **presets** and **default configurations**, and **not plugins** or other **tools**.

- Default or recommended settings from the linter (e.g. eslint:recommended)
- Airbnb
- Standard JS (the preset, **not** the tool)
- Google
- Prettier (the preset, **not** the tool)

Other - Write In

Other - Write In

Other - Write In

Importance of Rule Categories

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers

("ESLint")

18. Which of the ESLint categories do you consider to be important to include in configurations?

Documentation on the ESLint categories is available at <http://eslint.org/docs/rules>.

	Unimportant	Slightly important	Neutral/Not applicable	Important	Very important
Stylistic Issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Possible Errors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ECMAScript 6	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Best Practices	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Node.js and CommonJS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strict Mode	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Variables	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Importance of Rules in Possible Errors Category

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

19. Rank the importance of each of these rules in the Possible Errors category.

Each rule in the following list contains a [link to its documentation](http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#possible-errors), also available at <http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#possible-errors>.

	Unimportant	Slightly important	Neutral/Not applicable	Important	Very important
no-extra-boolean-cast (disallow unnecessary boolean casts, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-unreachable (disallow unreachable code after return, throw, continue, and break statements, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-unc-assign (disallow reassigning function declarations, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-console (disallow the use of console, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-empty (disallow empty block statements, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-extra-parens (disallow unnecessary parentheses, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-dupe-keys (disallow duplicate keys in object literals, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-inner-declarations (disallow variable or function declarations in nested blocks, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-cond-assign (disallow assignment operators in conditional expressions, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-invalid-regexp (disallow invalid regular expression strings in RegExp constructors, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-constant-condition (disallow constant expressions in conditions, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-irregular-whitespace (disallow irregular whitespace outside of strings and comments, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
valid-jsdoc (enforce valid JSDoc comments, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-extra-semi (disallow unnecessary semicolons, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

20. If you would like to explain your choices in the above question, or if you would like to mention other rules in this category that you find particularly important, please do so here.

Importance of Rules in Best Practices Category

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

21. Rank the importance of each of these rules in the Best Practices category.

Each rule in the following list contains a **link to its documentation**, also available at <http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#best-practices>.

	Unimportant	Slightly important	Neutral/Not applicable	Important	Very important
wrap-iife (require parentheses around immediate function invocations, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-param-reassign (disallow reassigning function parameters, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
curly (enforce consistent brace style for all control statements, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-multi-spaces (disallow multiple spaces, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-unused-expressions (disallow unused expressions, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
eqeqeq (require the use of === and !==, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-with (disallow with statements, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
consistent-return (require return statements to either always or never specify values, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-caller (disallow the use of arguments.caller or arguments.callee, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-eval (disallow the use of eval(), doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-warning-comments (disallow specified warning terms in comments, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
vars-on-top (require var declarations be placed at the top of their containing scope, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-extend-native (disallow extending native types, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-redeclare (disallow variable redeclaration, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

22. If you would like to explain your choices in the above question, or if you would like to mention other rules in this category that you find particularly important, please do so here.

Importance of Rules in Variables Category

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

23. Rank the importance of each of these rules in the Variables category.

Each rule in the following list contains a **link to its documentation**, also available at <http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#variables>.

	Unimportant	Slightly important	Neutral/Not applicable	Important	Very important
no-undef-init (disallow initializing variables to undefined, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-restricted-globals (disallow specified global variables, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-undef (disallow the use of undeclared variables unless mentioned in /*global */ comments, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-label-var (disallow labels that share a name with a variable, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-shadow-restricted-names (disallow identifiers from shadowing restricted names, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-catch-shadow (disallow catch clause parameters from shadowing variables in the outer scope, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
init-declarations (require or disallow initialization in variable declarations, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-shadow (disallow variable declarations from shadowing variables declared in the outer scope, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-use-before-define (disallow the use of variables before they are defined, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-undefined (disallow the use of undefined as an identifier, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-delete-var (disallow deleting variables, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
no-unused-vars (disallow unused variables, doc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

24. If you would like to explain your choices in the above question, or if you would like to mention other rules in this category that you find particularly important, please do so here.

Importance of Rules in Stylistic Issues Category

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

25. Rank the importance of each of these rules in the Stylistic Issues category.

Each rule in the following list contains a [link to its documentation](http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#stylistic-issues), also available at <http://eslint.org/docs/rules/#stylistic-issues>.

Unimportant Slightly important Neutral/Not applicable Important Very important

space-before-function-paren (enforce consistent spacing before function definition opening parenthesis, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
quotes (enforce the consistent use of either backticks, double, or single quotes, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
comma-style (enforce consistent comma style, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
space-before-blocks (enforce consistent spacing before blocks, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
func-names (require or disallow named function expressions, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
semi (require or disallow semicolons instead of ASI, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
comma-dangle (require or disallow trailing commas, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
no-underscore-dangle (disallow dangling underscores in identifiers, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
eol-last (require or disallow newline at the end of files, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
no-ternary (disallow ternary operators, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
brace-style (enforce consistent brace style for block, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
indent (enforce consistent indentation, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
linebreak-style (enforce consistent linebreak style, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				
max-len (enforce a maximum line length, doc)	<input type="radio"/>				

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Which linter(s) have you used?"

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it." #11 is one of the following answers ("ESLint")

26. If you would like to explain your choices in the above question, or if you would like to mention other rules in this category that you find particularly important, please do so here.

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

27. In your previous experience with using a linter, which challenges have you faced?

Check all that apply. If other challenges than those that are listed apply, please add them.

- Creating or maintaining configurations
- Enabling rules in an existing project
- Agreeing on which rules to use within a team
- Enforcing rules in a team
- The lack of analysis for dynamic features of JavaScript
- The presence of false positives (a **wrongly** indicated error/warning)
- Too many warnings/errors outputted from the linter
- No challenges
- Other - Write In
- Other - Write In
- Other - Write In

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

PIPING Piped From Question 11. (Which linter(s) have you used?)

Check all that apply. If you have used a linter that is not listed here, please add it.)

Final Remarks

LOGIC Hidden unless: Question "Have you ever used a linter in a JavaScript project?" #9 is one of the following answers ("Yes")

28. If you have any suggestions on how to improve linters for JavaScript, please add them here.

29. If you have any comments on the survey or on the topic, please add them here.

30. If you would like to receive the results of this study, please leave your email here.

Results are only used **anonymously**. Your email will **not be shared** with anyone and you will **not receive** any other emails than the results of this study.

31. If you would like to have a chance of winning a 50 dollar Amazon gift voucher, please leave your email here.

Results are only used **anonymously**. Your email will **not be shared** with anyone and you will **not receive** any other emails than a notification if you win the gift voucher (and results if you also registered above).

Thank You!

Thank you for taking our survey. Your response is very important to us.
